

For several years now Jonathan Prag (Professor of Ancient History in the Faculty and tutorial fellow at Merton College) has been developing an online digital corpus of the inscriptions of ancient Sicily: *I.Sicily* (<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/>). He has recently won an ERC Advanced Grant to develop the Crossreads project, which will explore the epigraphic culture of the island in much greater depth. Here he explains some of the thinking behind that project.

If you try to study the history of ancient Sicily through the *Cambridge Ancient History*, you will encounter a striking phenomenon: volumes 3–7 contain a number of substantial chapters dedicated to the history of the island, beginning with Greek colonisation in the west in the eighth and seventh centuries BC, and continuing down to the third century BC with chapters on Agathocles, Pyrrhus and the Punic Wars. But from the Punic Wars onwards, Sicily disappears from view, except for occasional pages in thematic chapters. As the nineteenth-century German historian of Sicily, Adolph Holm, put it (Holm 1898: 67), “After the fall of Syracuse and Agrigento, the importance of Sicily was far from that of before; a Roman province has its own history to only a very limited degree.” It is hardly coincidental there is no ancient narrative account for the island after the sack of Syracuse by Rome in 212 BC. That situation is compounded by the fact that the only substantial texts to mention Sicily thereafter are Diodorus Siculus’ account of the great slave revolts of the second century BC,

and Cicero’s monumental invective against the notorious figure of Gaius Verres. This makes it easy to construct a narrative of Sicilian history that, in prioritising Hellenic culture (more visible than others in the spectacular temples and other physical remains on the island), concludes that the island went into an irreparable decline with the Roman conquest (and implicitly is scarcely worth of study). In correspondence with his co-author Denis Mack-Smith, Moses Finley, author of the only modern English single-volume account of the island in antiquity, wrote “If you start the whole story of outside alien invaders with them [the Greeks], you are left with the obviously intolerable position that the pre-Greek Sicels etc. are the only true Sicilians. I think we must treat the Greeks apart, not as colonialists but as genuine Sicilians (they were there long enough).”

Where else can we turn for an understanding of the ‘the crossroads of the Mediterranean’, Braudel’s ‘continent in miniature’, and the interactions of Sikels, Elymians, Phoenicians, Greeks, Carthaginians, Oscan-speaking Italians, Romans, Jews, Christians and many more? Archaeology is of course one option, but if you want the ancient stones to speak, epigraphy is another, providing us with a wealth of ancient texts on stone and many other materials, in many different languages. Easier said than done, however.

The first published corpus of Sicilian inscriptions was produced in 1624 by Georgio Gualtieri (the Austrian scholar Georg Walther), containing

some 357 texts from Sicily and the surrounding islands. Gualtherus, and his successors such as the Principe di Torremuzza (two editions, 1769/1784) simply recorded texts in whatever language they found them, by location. However, with the rise of the great corpus projects of the 19th century, which sought to produce comprehensive records of the epigraphic texts, languages were split off into discreet projects and corpora (*Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum*, *Inscriptiones Graecae* – and the less complete/successful *Corpus Inscriptionum Semiticarum*), with the result that texts

Fig. 1. An Oscan dedicatory inscription

that originally stood next to each other were completely separated and could not easily be reunited. These projects also prioritised Greek and Latin, and that focus has continued through much of the subsequent scholarship. To take one particularly neat example, the inscriptions of ancient Messina were recently republished by the Messina university epigraphist Irma Bitto (*Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina*, 2001); however, the important contemporary Oscan inscriptions (Fig. 1) find no place in this work and remain relegated to a distinct and more obscure publication tradition (recently

Fig. 2. Sicily: the distribution of Latin epigraphy.

Fig. 3. Sicily: the distribution of Archaic epigraphy.

the crossroads of the ancient Mediterranean

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rescued, however by M. Crawford et al., *Imagines Italicae*, 2011). Furthermore, such corpora have traditionally tended to prioritise monumental texts on stone and metal, often passing over both the more fragmentary texts and the less formal texts on ceramic and other portable objects (so-called *instrumentum domesticum*).

In addition to the separation of texts by language (and/or museum collection, and/or locale), the rapid increase in new material, which came with the rise of archaeology on the island from the later nineteenth

century onwards, quickly outpaced the ability of systematic publication to keep track of new texts. Consequently, any systematic study of the Sicilian material became increasingly challenging, to say the least. In order to begin to be able to say something about the linguistic and cultural interactions on the island as evidenced by the thousands of ancient texts that survive (I currently estimate between four and five thousand texts on stone from the island in antiquity; *CIL X* and *IG XIV* each published c.500), a new comprehensive corpus has become necessary. Coincidentally, the rise of digital methods in epigraphy, and in particular the

EpiDoc TEI XML standard (<https://sourceforge.net/p/epidoc/wiki/Home/>) for encoding epigraphic texts and the information about them in a machine-readable and actionable format, mean that such a corpus can incorporate far more information (and imagery), in a far more flexible fashion, than the inevitable limitations imposed by traditional paper publication.

With the support of the University's John Fell Fund (and significant technical work by James Cummings, formerly of Oxford University IT Services, and James Chartrand, of Open Sky Solutions), we have steadily transformed a personal database, originally constructed between 2001 and 2004, into an EpiDoc corpus, published online since 2017 as *I.Sicily* (<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk> and <https://isicily.org>). On the one hand, *I.Sicily* makes the epigraphic texts of Sicily freely available to both the public and the research community as never before. On the other, the data makes it possible to begin to analyse the Sicilian epigraphic landscape more easily and in more depth than ever before.

Through the data in *I.Sicily*, it is possible to trace the changing patterns of epigraphic culture on the island, over the entire sweep of antiquity (seventh century BC to approximately the seventh century AD). At present, this analysis is limited to texts engraved on stone. At its most basic, this allows us to trace the changing use of languages for public epigraphy over time on the island. This does not, of course, necessarily

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correspond to the languages in daily use on the island – although close analysis of the texts, particularly more private texts such as funerary inscriptions, does have considerable potential to reveal features of local language use and of potential interference between languages. In the case of Sicily, what becomes predominantly clear is that while Greek is the dominant epigraphic language in the pre-Roman period, for the first three centuries of the Imperial period Latin to some extent takes over – only to fade more rapidly than Greek into the background again. The well known Latin 'epigraphic habit' is particularly obviously an Augustan-to-Severan phenomenon in Sicily, given that the Roman conquest took place some two centuries before Latin epigraphy appears in any significant way on the island, and Roman rule continued well beyond its demise; the primary focal points for Latin inscriptions are the veteran colonies established by Augustus, and the cities upgraded to colonial status in the Severan period (Fig. 2); exceptions to this correlation are few and mostly easily explained).

One notable feature in the early period is the extent to which substantial epigraphic practice on stone is concentrated in the areas of Greek and Phoenician colonisation, with Mozia's *tophet* sanctuary and Selinunte's necropoleis and sanctuaries providing primary areas of epigraphic activity (Fig. 3). The growing differences between Phoenicio-Punic epigraphic practice (which continues at scale in Carthage in the Hellenistic period, but largely

scription from Messina (ISic 1620).

Fig. 4. Sicily: the distribution of Hellenistic epigraphy.

Fig. 5. Types of stone in Sicilian inscriptions (7th – 5th century BC).

Fig. 6. Types of stone in Sicilian inscriptions (4th – 1st century BC).

Fig. 7 (below left). The 4th-century AD funerary inscription of Aurelius Samohil from Catania (ISic 781).

disappears

in Sicily with the sack of Mozia and the apparent Hellenisation of the Punic settlements of Solunto, Panormus and Lilybaeum) and the rapidly developing phenomenon of urban public epigraphy in Greek Hellenistic Sicily is revealed in the correlation between increasing urbanisation and epigraphy on the island in the Hellenistic period (Fig. 4). This shift is also clearly visible in the increasing diversification of materials on which these texts are engraved, with a rise in high-cost imported materials such as marble in the same period (Figs. 5–6).

These few preliminary glances at patterns in the epigraphic culture of the island give a foretaste of what the Crossreads project hopes to achieve. *I.Sicily* started as a collection of very basic data about the texts on stone (material, typology, chronology, etc.). More recently, and in the opening phase of Crossreads, the focus has moved towards making sure not only that that ‘metadata’ is comprehensive, but also that the actual text of every inscription is fully checked and encoded. *I.Sicily* to date has only focused upon stone texts (much like the majority of earlier corpora), of which c. 70% are funerary inscriptions (Fig. 7), while many of the rest are monumental public texts, like the Oscan inscription above. However, there are perhaps as many texts again, of very different sorts, to be found on metal (including curse tablets, of which Sicily is a rich source), ceramic, and other objects and materials (Fig. 8). Many of these are much less formal, more private texts, such as ownership graffiti on pottery (a category which, e.g., provides the

almost the only evidence for the Elymian language in Archaic western Sicily); others relate to economic activity, such as the stamps to be found on bricks and pottery – or even the legends on coinage, which are rarely included in epigraphic corpora.

The first year of the Crossreads project will be devoted to completing the work of corpus-building, revising and improving all the existing entries, and expanding the corpus to include the full range of other types of text. Thereafter, we aim to exploit that corpus in a much broader range of ways in order to maximise the potential of such a cross-lingual, cross-material, and typologically inclusive dataset. Three sub-projects, led by separate post-doctoral specialists, will focus on three areas: linguistics, petrography, and palaeography. In the area of linguistics, a number of major projects have already developed methods for annotating digital texts with information on the morphology of language and syntax; at the same time, recent work on Sicilian epigraphy has begun, with much success, to apply the methods and approaches of socio-linguistics to analysing points of language contact and interference. This work has cast new light on the nature of cultural interaction on the island, observing, e.g., North African influence on the Latin-speaking communities and eastern Mediterranean influence in the Greek-speaking communities (the majority of communities, however, displaying significant levels of bilingualism). However, to develop these insights fully, both in time and space, entails a much more systematic analysis of the entirety of the available texts. In the field of palaeography, new tools, developed primarily in the field of mediaeval manuscript studies, will enable us, almost for the first time, to

undertake a systematic, ‘objective’ analysis of the letterforms in use across the island over more than a millennium; when this is combined with the ability to compare letterforms and so writing systems across different languages, a whole new area of ‘language contact’ opens up. Lastly, while the use of stone and the monumentalisation of text is a well-observed and widely discussed phenomenon, very rarely does this incorporate any sort of rigorous, scientifically based analysis of the stone employed. We aim to develop the first petrographic database for Sicily, conducting full petrological analysis of the stone inscriptions of the island. Such a resource will move the analysis far beyond the basic observation about imported marble noted above, and opens up a host of possible insights on the socio-economic aspects of public epigraphy (as well as providing a valuable resource for the archaeology of the island in general). A final benefit of building all this data into a digital corpus is that these analyses will not exist in isolation, as discrete projects; it is the possibility of combining these different approaches and their insights that makes Crossreads truly exciting, re-reading texts at the crossroads of the Mediterranean.

Fig. 8. A 1st-century BC bronze tablet with an honorary decree for the priests of Apollo Nemenios, from Halaisa (SEG 59.1100).